

SYNCHRONIZATION MECHANISM IN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETING

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the factors which make the synchronization mechanism in simultaneous interpreting work, highlighting the cognitive aspects of it. It describes simultaneous translation as a classic case of distribution of attention because it combines several cognitive tasks, the execution of which occurs more or less simultaneously.

Key words: *Cognitive tasks, automaticity, synchronization mechanism, selective attention, long-term memory.*

Introduction.

The basis of the cognitive synchronization mechanism, in our opinion, is distribution of the translator's attention between different mechanisms/operations. When discussing issues related to simultaneous listening and speaking one cannot ignore the factor of automaticity. According to the general opinion, when improving this skill subsequently, it no longer requires much attention and significant cognitive efforts. Therefore, tasks, the skill of working out of which is brought to perfection, according to S. Lambert, are performed automatically and are not subject to disruptions due to insufficient distribution of attention [Lambert, 2004: 296].

Main part.

Simultaneous translation is a classic case of distribution of attention because it combines several cognitive tasks, the execution of which occurs more or less simultaneously. Engaged cognitive operation of attention distribution, when a simultaneous interpreter exercises control over two or more tasks (listening to oral messages in the original language and its translation into another language), while while checking the verbalization of their own translations.

In addition, the interpreter occasionally reads passages from the written version of the speech speaker in order to find the best match for specific words and expressions.

P. Padilla et al. (Padilla et al., 1995) give a detailed description involved operations. They believe that the translator must be able to store a new lexical item in its working memory, use search for its meaning in long-term memory, associate new information with the one what is stored in the translator's memory, and at the same time verbalize translation of the previous lexical unit.

This very difficult task carried out over a fairly long period of time which the simultaneous interpreter loads and releases at high speed their working memory [Ibid.: 69].

The ability to distribute attention among several different tasks performed simultaneously is explained by three hypotheses:

– extra-effort hypothesis: increase resource requirements for simultaneous execution of tasks requires large efforts from the translator;

– hypothesis about the shift of attention (alternation-of-attention hypothesis): translators perform different tasks not strictly simultaneously; they are studying quickly shift attention from one task to another;

– hypothesis about the automation of cognitive operations (automatic-mental activities hypothesis): having developed the ability to perform tasks with distribution of attention, the translator no longer needs control every cognitive operation, because some of them were performed automatically.

E. (Camayd-Freixas, (2011) believes that with several tasks in synchronous translation require our attention. In particular, mental formulation of a translation option interferes with the verbalization of the previous one fragment, which, in turn, makes it difficult to perceive and understand incoming auditory information from the speaker. Therefore, our attention should be flexible and mobile: we can tune our attention to performing other tasks, but we should never turn it off.

In this case, a good volume in the headphones will help simultaneous interpreter understands the speaker's speech better and holds it longer in memory, following the speaker's thoughts. Headphone volume should be as comfortable as possible, depending on the translation situation.

One of the important aspects of mobile listening is the constant tracking the main idea of an unfolding oral message. Holding the "thread" of thought is of great importance for ensuring speed and accuracy of simultaneous translation. According to E. Camayd-Freixas,, mobile listening is listening in a state of relaxed attention in which words pass through the auditory analyzer, and the translator monitors their meaning, without fixing attention on them, without dwelling on a particular word or idea.

Indeed, selective attention is a key element simultaneous translation, according to the scientist. The main thing is to be as efficient as possible, use the single-channel attention of a simultaneous interpreter, understand, how much attention should be paid to listening and speaking, and when switch from one task to another.

In his model of fluid attention in simultaneous translation, E. Camayd-Freixas, points out that the attention concentration curve has the shape of a surf a wave that rises until the interpreter formulates the interpretation of a segment of the message. At that moment, this "wave" breaks down, flowing smoothly through the phases of speech production and control.

Straightaway after formulation, selective attention is shifted back to listening and the process is repeated for a new segment of oral communication on original language. To represent the speed at which a given process, note that the time of a human reaction (for example, the time between formulation of the phrase and its verbalization) is approximately 200 milliseconds, i.e. 0.2 seconds. Thus, a simultaneous interpreter usually processes 2 -3 words in a second. This is related to two important psycholinguistic observations: optimal listening speed for uncomplicated comprehension is 170 words per minute; while the optimal speed of translation in order to avoid negative stressful situations should be about 120 words per minute. The simultaneous interpreter has to distribute own resources, use abbreviations/omissions, accelerate your pace by an increase in stress load, which inevitably leads to faster fatigue of a translator than a speaker [Ibid.: 13].

In their works, various scientists noted that simultaneous interpreter has to perform several cognitive operations almost simultaneously processes 2-3 words per second.

At the same time, information processing by people can pass through only one channel (listening or speaking). We are closer to the idea expressed by E. Camayd-Freixas, that the attention of an interpreter in simultaneous translation should be mobile and that you need to learn how to distribute it in the right time between basic cognitive mechanisms/operations.

Based on the analysis of the above works, in our opinion, cognitive mechanism of synchronization includes the following operations:

- a shift in attention between listening and speaking (moving attention);
- retention of the main idea of the statement;
- maintaining a comfortable speed of translation verbalization (due to application of various translation strategies);
- leveling the influence of negative stressful load.

In conditions of simultaneous translation from a foreign language into a native the translator should focus on the perception of foreign speech, since speech production in the native language does not require much attention.

However, when a translator has to translate from his native language into foreign, his attention will shift towards the generation of statements in a foreign language. Despite this, it is necessary to pay significant attention and perception in the native language in order to prevent loss of important information. For this, it is extremely important in every lesson.

Conclusion.

To conclude, taking into account the factors mentioned above that affect the performance of cognitive mechanisms, we will separately dwell on two more aspects

that are typical for the cognitive system of simultaneous translation as a whole. This lag of the translator from the speaker and psycho-emotional training.

The lag of the simultaneous interpreter from the speaker (ear-voice span) characterizes some time that is used by the translator for making any decision. In other words, due to this lag all cognitive mechanisms of simultaneous translation function.

For training such a lag behind the speaker's speech, the simultaneous interpreter should be able to store a certain amount of information in short-term memory, constantly updating it: removing the used information and uploading the new one.

Psycho-emotional training consists in such tuning of the nervous systems in which the influence of stress factors is minimized and does not lead to a decrease and / or loss of the ability of an interpreter to perform its activities. Psycho-emotional training can be carried out with using hardware methods or without them.

It aims to develop stress resistance of the interpreter to negative factors of the different situation of synchronous translation. Simultaneous interpreters should be able to level the stressful load both on the eve of simultaneous translation activities, and during its time when unforeseen adverse conditions may develop for its implementation.

References:

1. Camayd-Freixas, E. Cognitive theory of simultaneous interpreting and training / E. Camayd-Freixas // Proceedings of the 52nd Conference of the American Translators Association. – New York: ATA, 2011.
2. Padilla, B., Bajo, T. Hacia un modelo de memoria y atención de interpretación simultánea / B. Padilla, T. Bajo // Quaderns: Revista de traducció. – 1998. – Vol.2. – P.107–117. (In Spanish).
3. Padilla, P., Bajo, T., Cañas, J.J., Padilla, F. Cognitive processes of memory in simultaneous interpretation / P. Padilla, T. Bajo, J.J. Cañas, F. Padilla // Topics in Interpreting Research / edited by J. Tommola. – University of Turku, Centre for Translation and Interpreting, 1995. – P.61-71.
4. Olimova, D. (2022). About The Mechanisms That Provide Understanding Of The Original Text While Speaking Text In Target Language: About The Mechanisms That Provide Understanding Of The Original Text While Speaking Text In Target Language. Центр Научных Публикаций (buxdu.Uz), 23(23). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/8137
5. Olimova, D. (2021). Важность формирования навыков автономного обучения у студентов при преподавании иностранного языка. Центр научных публикаций (buxdu.Uz), 5(5). извлечено от http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/2398
6. Olimova Dilfuza Zokirovna., Continuity And Discreteness Of Simultaneous

- Interpreting. Theory And Analytical Aspects Of Recent Research 1 (5), 720-723, 2022
7. Olimova, D. Z., & Mahmudova, M. D. (2022). Political Discourse And Translation. Research And Education, 1(3), 176–179. Retrieved from <http://researchedu.org/index.php/re/article/view/577>
8. Olimova D.Z., Turayeva Z.A. The Peculiar Complexity Of Translating Uzbek Classical Poetry Into English (Based On The English Translations Of Navoi's Ghazals) Web of Scientist:International Scientific Research Journal.,Vol.3,Issue 5,May,2022.-P 94-97.
9. Khaydarova, L. . (2023). Teaching Listening Comprehension as a Part of Educational Process at School. Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education, 2(3), 259–263. Retrieved from <https://univerpubl.com/index.php/semantic/article/view/778>
10. Khaydarova L., Isheryakova J. Economic Translation As A Concept And Its Practical Issues //Academic Research In Modern Science. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 9. – С. 85-88
11. Khaydarova L., Joanna I. Teaching English Grammar Through Interactive Methods //Innovative Development In The Global Science. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 174-178.
12. Xaydarova, L. (2022). «Global Value Of Health And Its Practical Implementation In The Form Of Actual Daily Practices. Центр Научных Публикаций (Buxdu.Uz), 8(8). Извлечено От http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/5779
13. L. Khaydarova. "The Usage Of Interactive Methods While Developing Reading Skills Of Young Learners" Science and innovation, vol. 1, no. B7, 2022, pp. 324-328. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7236481
14. Zokirovna, Olimova Dilfuza. "GENERAL CONCEPT OF COGNITIVE MECHANISMS." Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal 3.12 (2022): 735-740.
15. Zokirova, N. S. (2022). Extralinguistic Features of Professional Discourse as Metalinguistic Nature of Special Communication. Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture, 3(6), 80-84. Retrieved from <https://cajlpc.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJLPC/article/view/383>
16. G Khamraeva, D Olimova – Benefits of using role plays in teaching languages. Научная дискуссия: инновации в современном мире, 2017,п. 97-101.
17. Olimova, D. Z. (2021). Transfer of modality in translation (modal verbs and their equivalents, modal words). Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 12, 220-22.